

8T – Quantum Manifolds

Dedicated to R.P. Feynman

Who left us 33 years ago

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series in net variation representation, alongside with the main equation of variational manifolds, it is possible to construct a new kind of manifold which takes into account the probability of Emission/ Absorption of net curvature. that probability is varying according to the number of discrete net variation which the lepton has absorbed. Those are Quantum manifolds, or as a tribute to a one of the all-time greats, The Feynman manifolds.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin N = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

In page fifty-five in the 8T thesis, the primorial explained the phenomena of particle wave duality, by additional photon causing a shift in the spin by additional half unit. Such a shift is leading to a spin no longer Bosonic. So it is impossible to measure a photon without interfering with his nature, shifting it from wave to a particle.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow 2N_2 + \frac{3}{2} \quad (2.19)$$

Up to this point in the construction of the 8T, our theory we have used the Lorentz manifold of the form $s = (M, g)$ as the manifold was parametrized onto "s" M stands as the matric and 'g' as the Ricci flow. Since the 8T in essence is describing vanishing arbitrary amount of curvature spikes (1.48) and non-vanishing curvature spikes (1.49) as Bosons due to their prime number feature, we must add this probability parameter onto the manifold.

$$s = (M, g) \rightarrow (M, g, \mathcal{F})$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}: N_V \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_i \quad (2.4)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$\mathcal{F} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \mathcal{P}_i$$

$$N_V = +3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{i=3}$$

$$\mathcal{P}_i \in [0, 1]$$

To each net variation element, N_V there exist a parameterized unique probability of emission or absorption onto the lepton from the second term (for simplicity sake the first term is ignored) and above given by (2.4), the summation of all the probability than taken onto \mathcal{F} , which was chosen as tribute to one of the all-time greats, Richard Feynman. The new manifold can be than considered as the Feynman manifold. For simplicity sake, we will analyze the third coupling term, electromagnetism.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Suppose that the electron just emitted a Boson, a net variation of discrete prime amount, and a distinct electron has just absorbed it. The electron that just absorbed it is described by the process:

$$(e \leftarrow \gamma) \rightarrow e$$

The important point is that the electron, which absorbed and the electron that emitted, now differ in terms of their probability. The probability of the electron that absorbed is higher as it has additional term of distinct prime curvature within it. The result of all this is that we can introduce a superscript on the electron to sum the number of elements, i.e. prime bosons it has within it, and according to this number the probability of emission/absorption is varying.

$$e \rightarrow e^{\mathcal{K}}$$

$$\mathcal{K} \in \mathbb{R}$$

For the electron that absorbed a photon, the new parameterization will be:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^{+1}$$

For the electron that emitted the photon the probability in the new parameterization will be:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^0$$

We need to introduce a sub-script to differentiate the two electrons, so overall:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^{+1} \rightarrow e_1^{+1}$$

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^0 \rightarrow e_0^0$$

The point is now that each of those leptons has a distinct probability, we need another superscript on the probability parameter to differentiate between two elements of the same coupling kind:

$$e_1^{+1} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{i=5}^{e=1}$$

$$e_0^0 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{i=5}^{e=0}$$

Since that superscript is the summation of the absorbed net curvature of distinct amount, we can easily conclude that the probability of this lepton to emit is higher, because of the summation of the superscript. That is:

$$\mathcal{P}_{i=5}^{e=1} > \mathcal{P}_{i=5}^{e=0}$$

That the probability of emission is higher due to the higher subscript. It is also proportional to the superscript, the higher it is, and the higher should be the probability:

$$\mathcal{P}_i \propto \mathcal{K}$$

The summation of all probabilities across all the coupling terms on the manifold is manifested in the summation:

$$\mathcal{F} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_v} \mathcal{P}_i^X$$

The subscript is the kind of net variation:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}: N_v \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_i \quad (2.4)$$

The superscript is the element which absorbed

$$X = e_i; \quad i \in \mathbb{R}$$

The term can be re-scaled:

$$\mathcal{F} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_v} \mathcal{P}_i^X = 1 \quad (2.41)$$

In (2.41) we need to sum all the elements in X.

$$X = \sum_{i=1}^K e_i \rightarrow X_S$$

This results in the final form of (2.41):

$$\mathcal{F} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_v} \mathcal{P}_i^{X_S} = 1 \quad (2.41.A)$$

The end result is a varying manifold which take into account the probably of emission due to absorption, that is due to a superscript summation on the lepton. The final form of (2.41) sums over all the leptons of a certain kind which injected onto \mathcal{F} . These are Quantum manifolds, in other words. We can also make a prediction that the electron would aspire to the lowest summation on the superscript, which means to the lowest energy level possible, or to the least amount of prime distinct curvature within it.

$$e_{\mathcal{N}}^{\mathcal{K}} \rightarrow e_{\mathcal{N}}^0$$

For some time parameter:

$$t \rightarrow \infty$$

Another way to state is the exact same thing:

$$\frac{\partial p_i}{\partial t} \neq 0$$

That is to state that leptons has a varying probability of emission or absorption over time, and if we aspire to be more brave, according to the superscript prediction, the probability of **emission** should be lower, and aspire zero over time. One can only consider emission has the superscript is describing how much distinct prime amounts the lepton contains. The prediction about absorption seems to be a somewhat more complicated, and depends upon the expansion of the manifolds as an example, thus it will be left out of this paper.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad